

Association between farmer characteristics and level of knowledge with level of cholinesterase enzymes on farmers in Batu city, East Java

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ABSTRACT

Uncontrolled use of pesticides can cause health problems for farmers. Farmers can be exposed to pesticides at the time of application, either through the skin, mouth or nose/breathing. This study aims to determine the association between farmer's characteristics and level of knowledge with the level of cholinesterase enzymes in the sample of blood of farmers in Batu City, East Java. This research was conducted in January - May 2015. Blood sampling was carried out on 48 farmers in Sumber Brantas Village, Bumiaji District and 22 farmers in Pendem Village, Junrejo District. The study used an analytic observational design with a cross sectional approach. Measurement of cholinesterase enzyme levels in blood samples is carried out with the rapid test kit (Cholinesterase kit, Tintometer®). The results showed that farmers in Sumber Brantas Village experienced severe poisoning of 4.2%, moderate poisoning 70.8%, mild poisoning 22.9%, and non-poisoning 2.1%. None of the farmers from Pendem Village experienced severe poisoning (0%), 50% of farmers were moderately poisoned, 40.9% were mild poisoned and 9.1% were not poisoned. Cholinesterase enzyme levels were positively correlated with farmer age, sex, farmers' last day of contact with pesticides, distance of houses to agricultural land, and level of knowledge about pesticides, but negatively correlated with the level of education and nutritional status of farmers. A good level of knowledge will reduce the risk of pesticide poisoning which is characterized by high levels of cholinesterase in the blood.

Keywords: correlation, level of knowledge, cholinesterase, farmers

INTRODUCTION

The pattern of pesticide use by farmers tends to be out of control. Farmers use pesticides not on the basis of indications for pest control, but they implement a blanket cover system, there are pests or not, plants are still sprayed with pesticides (Achmadi, 2005). Uncontrolled use of pesticides will result in health problems for the farmers themselves and the environment. Negative impacts by agrochemical materials can be classified into two types: (1) impacts on humans, such as poisoning, including acute and chronic poisoning such as

carcinogenic, teratogenic and biological enlargement, and (2) environmental impacts including pollution and ecosystem disturbances (Takagi and Ueji, 1997).

Pesticides, especially from organophosphate groups that enter the human body affect nerve function by inhibiting the action of cholinesterase, an essential chemical (enzyme) in delivering impulses along the nerve fibers (Achmadi, 2005; Syarief, 2007). The level of pesticide poisoning from the organophosphate group is measured based on the activity of the cholinesterase in the blood (Dirjen PPM PLP, 1992; Syarief, 2007). Risk factors related to the incidence of organophosphate pesticide poisoning include age, sex, knowledge, experience, skills, education, use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), nutritional status and pesticide handling practices. While the critical phase that must be considered is the way of storing pesticides, how to mix pesticides, how to use pesticides and handling after the use of pesticides (Achmadi, 2005).

In 2006 an examination of cholinesterase activity was carried out in 550 vegetable farmers located in 7 sub-districts in Magelang District in Central Java. The results showed 99.8% of the population experienced poisoning with details; 18.2% had severe poisoning; 72.73% experienced moderate poisoning; 8.9% experienced mild toxicity and only 0.18% are not poisoning (normal) (Labkesmas Magelang District, 2006; Prihadi, 2008; Priyanto, 2009). Batu City in East Java has the same characteristics as in Magelang district where many farmers cultivate vegetables and fruits.

This study aims to determine the association between farmer's characteristics and level of knowledge with the level of cholinesterase enzymes in the sample of blood of farmers in Batu City, East Java. Another goal is to determine the correlation between farmers characteristics and level of knowledge with the risk of pesticide poisoning to farmers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The cross-sectional study was used as the research design of this study. This method is to find out the exposure risk factors and the impacts generated through measurement at the same time (Sastroasmoro, 2002; Bachtiar, 2000). The study areas (Sumber Brantas village, Bumiaji District and Pendem village, Junrejo District, The city of Batu, East Java province) were purposively selected because there were mainly agricultural in the city of Batu. The simple random sampling was done to get 70 participants. Inclusion criteria were farmers, both male and female, aged more than 18, the level of hemoglobin ≥ 12 g/dL. Those with a history of liver failure, malnutrition, cardiovascular disease, taking anti-malarial drugs, taking amphetamine (Wilaiwan et al., 2015), suffer from diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease, tuberculosis, glaucoma, and not in physostigma treatment (Bachtiar, 2000), were excluded.

The materials used are questionnaire forms and reagents for

examination of blood cholinesterase levels consisting of: 0.112 g Bromine Thymol Blue (BTB) as indicator solution, 250 ml aquadestilata (CO₂ free) and 0.25 g Acetylcholine Perchlorate (ACP). The tools used are stationery, measuring height, scales, sphygmomometer, a set of cholinesterase test kits (Tintometer® Kit).

Blood sampling and measurement of cholinesterase levels

Analysis of cholinesterase levels is carried out quickly, immediately after taking blood samples from farmers. Blood sampling was carried out by officers from the Batu City Health Office in Sumber Brantas Village, Bumiaji District and Pendem Village, Junrejo District. Farmers who are the subject must have the inclusion as follows: farmers must do pesticide spraying activities, Blood sampling methods follow the procedures established by the Indonesian Ministry of Health.

Measurement of cholinesterase levels in blood samples is done with Cholinesterase kit (Tintometer®). This tool measures cholinesterase activity in the blood through a complete blood test or separately (red blood and plasma). WHO (1996) determined the threshold value of insecticide poisoning is the value of cholinesterase activity in blood grains reaching $\geq 70\%$ and in plasma $\geq 60\%$ of normal values. The procedure for measuring cholinesterase levels consists of 3 stages, 1) blood blanks preparation, 2) determination of reaction time (time zero and match), and 3) blood samples test.

Preparation of blood blank begins with taking 0.01 mL of control person blood into a test tube containing 1.0 mL of aquadest (free CO₂). Then the solution was transferred to a 2.5 ml cuvet and 1 sample blood test. The reaction time (time zero and match) was determined by entering 0.01 mL of control person blood into the test tube which contained 0.5 mL BTB solution. A blood solution is added with 0.5 ml of ACP solution into the tube and simultaneously press the start button on "stop watch" which is then called zero time. The solution is shaken until it dissolves and quickly pours to the cuvet and place it on the right comparator. Changes in the color of the solution are observed while rotating the disc until the result matches the standard color of 100%. The time obtained (match) is recorded, usually around 20-30 minutes depending on the local temperature. The time obtained is used for the standard "sample" blood reading time. Cholinesterase levels were tested by inserting 0.01 mL of the farmers' blood sample into a tube containing 0.5 mL of indicator solution (BTB). Then add 0.5 mL of ACP solution to the tube and shake until dissolved. The solution is transferred immediately to the cuvet and put into the right comparator. The reading of the results is in accordance with the match time.

Data of farmers Characteristic and level of knowledge were taken by questionnaire method. The principal researcher assessed the subjects by face to

face. Questionnaire consisted of two parts; part 1: obtain general information and part 2: obtain level of knowledge information about pesticides. General information include identity (name, age, sex, address), level of education, nutritional status (height and weight), last day of contact with pesticides, distance between house and agricultural land. The level of knowledge information about pesticides include the type, how to mix, how to store, and how to handle after application on the land). Scoring method was carried out to measure Characteristic and level of knowledge of pesticide from the representative farmers.

Data analysis

The level of pesticide poisoning is determined based on cholinesterase levels. If the cholinesterase level is 75%-100% in the normal category (no poisoning), cholinesterase levels are 50%-<75% including mild poisoning, 25%-<50% including moderate poisoning, and 0%-<25 % is categorized as heavy poisoning (Director General of PPM PLP, 1992; Syarief, 2007). Correlation between farmer characteristics and cholinesterase levels in farmer blood was analyzed using Pearson correlation coefficient test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

There are two criteria for farmers who are taken for blood samples, namely farmers in Sumber Brantas Village and farmers in Pendem Village. Farmers in Sumber Brantas village are vegetable farmers who use pesticides intensively, while farmers in Pendem village are rice farmers who have implemented semi / organic farming systems. Characteristics of farmers from the two villages have differences in age group, level of education, nutritional status and the last time contact with pesticides (Table 1).

Farmers can be exposed to pesticides at the time of application, either through the skin, mouth or nose / breathing. The active ingredients of pesticides that enter the human body will accumulate in the blood. If the concentration of a pesticide compound exceeds the maximum limit, it will cause metabolic disturbances. Pesticides can enter the human body because many factors include human negligence such as does not use safety equipment while working. These negligence can occur due to lack of knowledge about pesticides include how to store, how to apply, how to mix and handle post-application of pesticides. The results showed that farmers in Sumber Brantas and Pendem villages had a low level of knowledge about pesticides (scoring < 30), except in the knowledge of how to store pesticides (scoring > 17) (Table 2). Prihadi (2008) states that farmers who have a low level of knowledge will have a risk of poisoning by 4.27 times compared to farmers who have good knowledge.

Table 1. Characteristics of farmers

No	Parameter		Sumber	Pendem
			Brantas village (n=48)	village (n=22)
			%	
1	Sex	male	70.8	81.8
		female	29.2	18.2
2	Age group	young (≤ 39 y)	35.4	9.1
		old (> 39 y)	64.6	90.9
3	Level of education	no school	2.1	13.6
		not graduated from elementary school	14.6	22.7
		elementary school	16.7	36.4
		junior high school	31.3	13.6
		senior high school	31.3	13.6
		university	4.2	0.0
4	Nutritional status	good	62.5	50.0
		lack	37.5	50.0
5	The last time contact with pesticides	1 – 14 days	83.3	18.2
		more than 14 days	16.7	81.8
6	Home distance from agricultural land	1 – 1000 m	75.0	72.7
		More than 1000 m	25.0	27.3

Table 2. Level of knowledge about Pesticides

No	Parameter		Sumber Brantas	Pendem village
			village (n=48)	(n=22)
			(%)	
1	Pesticide	good	8.3	4.5
		lack	91.7	95.5
2	How to store	good	75.0	54.5
		lack	25.0	45.5
3	How to mix	good	0.0	0.0
		lack	100.0	100.0
4	How to apply	good	29.2	36.4
		lack	70.8	63.6
5	How to handle post-application	good	8.3	0.0
		lack	91.7	100.0

Pesticides enter the body through various methods, including through penetration of skin pores (90%) and through inhalation, digestion or other (10%). Therefore, the best way to prevent poisoning is to avoid direct contact and provide protection for body parts from pesticide exposure. The results of measurements of cholinesterase levels in farmers' blood showed that farmers who were intensive in using pesticides in Sumber Brantas village experienced higher levels of poisoning than in Pendem Village (Figure 1). The absence of heavily poisoned farmers in Pendem village due to the past three years many farmers have begun to reduce the use of chemical pesticides and conduct semi-organic farming systems.

Figure 3. Level of pesticide poisoning based on Cholinesterase levels in the blood of farmers

Cholinesterase levels were positively correlated with farmer age, sex, farmers' last day of contact with pesticides, distance of houses to agricultural land, and level of knowledge about pesticides, and negatively correlated with the level of education and nutritional status of farmers (Table 3).

The age of the farmer influences the level of cholinesterase concentration in the blood associated with the length of time the farmer works with pesticides during the cultivation process. The older the farmer, the longer working time with pesticides, which leads to lower cholinesterase levels in the blood as an indication of poisoning. Women tend to have higher cholinesterase levels than men. The last day of the farmer's contact with pesticides also had a significant effect, the shorter the time between the last day of contact with pesticides and the examination caused a low level of cholinesterase in the blood. The distance of the house is also influential because the pesticide compounds are volatile so that when spraying, pesticide compounds can move in the air, so that when spraying must consider the direction of the wind gusts. A good level of knowledge will reduce the risk of pesticide poisoning which is characterized by high levels of cholinesterase in the blood. Education level and nutritional status

are negatively correlated with cholinesterase levels in the blood of farmers.

Table 3. Matrix Correlation of cholinesterase levels with characteristics of farmers and level of knowledge about pesticides

Parameter	Level of cholinesterase	Age	sex	Level of education	Nutritional status	Last time contact with pesticides	Home distance from field	Level of knowledge about pesticides
Level of cholinesterase	1.0000	0.1770	0.0880	-0.0310	-0.2419*	0.3069**	0.0755	0.0955
age		1.0000	-0.0022	0.3770	0.0105	0.3895	-0.0133	-0.1503
sex			1.0000	-0.1634	-0.1432	0.2782	-0.1924	-0.1503
Level of education				1.0000	0.0214	-0.2086	-0.0696	-0.0377
Nutritional status					1.0000	-0.0885	0.0888	0.0070
Last time contact with pesticides						1.0000	0.0391	-0.2259
Home distance from field							1.0000	0.0513
Level of knowledge about pesticides								1.0000

N=70; $t_{0,05}=0,232$; $t_{0,01}=0,302$

CONCLUSIONS

This study resulted that farmers in Batu city, East Java province experienced severe poisoning of 2,88%, moderate poisoning 64,26%, mild poisoning 28,56%, and non-poisoning 4,30%. Cholinesterase enzyme levels were positively correlated with farmer age, farmers' last day of contact with pesticides, distance of houses to agricultural land, and level of knowledge about pesticides, but negatively correlated with the level of education and nutritional status of farmers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research was funded by the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture. We would like thank to head officer of Batu City Health Office and all of team of for their help in measurement of cholinesterase in farmers. We would like thank also to Head officer and Staff officer of Agricultural and Forestry Office of Batu City .

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